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Institute of Medical Sciences,
North Kolkata

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High Court, Kolkata

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CFI, Kolkata

Mrs. Susmita Banerjee

IEC Ref: CNCI-IEC-JC-2025-03

Date: 11.02.2025

Dr. Jayanta Chakrabarti
Director, CNCI

Sub.: IEC decision on review of the project submitted for approval.

Protocol Title: **QUEST: Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer: A Prospective Study on Quality of Life and Survival of Bladder Cancer patients using Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs).**

Study Site: Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, Kolkata

Expedited Review Meeting of IEC was conducted in physical mode on 7th February, 2025. The Chairman and members of the committee reviewed the project and other related documents submitted by you for the proposed study entitled "**QUEST: Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer: A Prospective Study on Quality of Life and Survival of Bladder Cancer patients using Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs).**"

The following documents were reviewed:

1. Project with Summary
2. Informed Consent Sheets
3. Administrative Approval
4. Academic/Scientific Committee approval

The committee should be informed:

- I. About the progress of the study annually
- II. Any changes in the protocol and patient information/ informed consent documents, prior to their implementation

The Project is approved by the IEC.

Final report of the study shall have to be submitted to the IEC in all cases, even when the study is abandoned for any reason(s).

Yours Sincerely,

Member Secretary
IEC, CNCI

Member Secretary

Institutional Ethics Committee
Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute
37, S. P. Mukherjee Road, Kolkata-700026

Chairman
IEC, CNCI

Chairman

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